

adding varying amounts of mineral acids to it, allowing the mixture to stand for 24 hours, and back-titrating the ascorbic acid left potentiometrically with iodine solutions.

FIG. 1. Independent co-ordinates (vide Table IA).

FIG. 2. (vide Table III)

In the first case, burette readings on the potentiometer were not stable before one hour. In order to prevent the loss of nitrous acid by decomposition, nitrite was added from the burette in very small portions. The atmosphere of CO_2 and the presence of a powerful reducing agent are enough to prevent this loss. On addition of each small portion of nitrite, readings on the potentiometer showed a continuous increase and after reaching a maximum value, which varied in each addition, the reading again decreased till a constant value was attained. To reach the point of inflection, it needed 2 hours or more for stable reading, specially when the HCl concentration was increased. In this way each potentiometric titration required at least 8 hours. The results are summarised in Table I (A and B) and in Fig. 1.

TABLE I
Ascorbic acid and HCl in the cell and $0.1M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in the burette.

Ascorbic acid taken.	Conc. of ascorbic acid.	Effective HCl conc.	Inflection at.	Moles of nitrite per mole A*.	Curve No. (Fig. 1)
A. HCl conc. is low.					
10 ml	0.950 ($M/200$)	$N/100$	0.95 ml	2.00	I
20	0.920	$N/60$	1.85	2.01	II
20	0.780	$N/50$	1.55	2.03	III
20	0.578	$N/40$	1.15	2.00	IV
20	0.570	$N/30$	1.05	2.00	V
B. HCl conc. is high.					
40	0.710	$N/20$	2.05	1.45	
40	0.837	$N/2$	2.40	1.43	
40	0.807	$2N$	2.00	1.23	
40	0.880	$6N$	2.00	1.13	
20	2.740	$10N$	3.00	1.09	

*A denotes ascorbic acid.

In the reverse case, no inflection in the titration curve was noticed if any of the two substances taken in the cell was in large excess. Satisfactory titrations were, however, possible if the two were taken in nearly equivalent proportions (not equimolar). The results are summarised in Table II. The back titrations of ascorbic acid by iodine (Table III, Fig. 2) were the least time-consuming as the stable potentials were recorded within 5 min. Table IV and Fig. 3 record the summary of the results obtained when H_2SO_4 is used in place of HCl and nitrite added from the burette. The effect of increased concentration of the acid on the stability of potentials, prominent in the case of HCl, was not noticed in the case of H_2SO_4 . Some titrations were also performed with mixtures of HCl and H_2SO_4 (Table V and Fig. 4).

TABLE II
Mixture of $NaNO_2$ and ascorbic acid (2:1) in the cell and
0.1N-HCl in the burette.

Ascorbic acid		$NaNO_2$		Inflection at.	Moles of $NaNO_2$ per mole A.
Vol. taken.	Conc.	Vol.	Conc.		
20 ml	0.548 (M/200)	1.1 ml	M/10	0.55 ml	2
20	0.502	10.0	M/100	0.50	2
20	0.530	11.0	M/100	0.50	2

TABLE III
* Mixture of $NaNO_2$ and ascorbic acid in the cell.
Excess of A back-titrated with N/10- I_2 soln. in burette; HCl added before titration.

Effective HCl concn.	Inflection at.	Moles HNO_2 /mole A.	Curve No. (Fig. 2).
N/100*	1.55 ml	2.0	I
N/10	1.40	1.8	II
2 N	1.10	1.4	III
4 N	1.10	1.4	IV
6 N	0.90	1.2	V

*1 Mole $NaNO_2$: 1.28 mole ascorbic acid (Δ).

TABLE IV

H_2SO_4 used in place of HCl; ascorbic acid in cell; 0.1M-NaNO₂ in the burette.

Vol. of A.	Conc. of A.	Effective conc. of H_2SO_4 .	Inflexion at.	Moles NaNO ₂ /mole A.	Curve No. (Fig. 3)
10 ml	<i>M</i> /100	<i>N</i> /20	2.05 ml	2	I
10	1.03(<i>M</i> /100)	<i>N</i> /2	2.00	2	II
10	0.947 "	<i>N</i>	1.80	2	III
10	0.947 "	2 <i>N</i>	1.85	2	IV

TABLE V

Mixtures of HCl and H_2SO_4 with ascorbic acid in the cell. 0.1M-NaNO₂ added from the burette.

Ascorbic acid.	HCl conc. (10ml).	H_2SO_4 conc. (10 ml).	Inflexion at.	Moles NaNO ₂ per mole A.	Curve No. (Fig. 4)
10 ml 1.03(<i>M</i> /100)	<i>N</i>	<i>N</i>	1.95 ml	1.89	I
10 " "	6 <i>N</i>	<i>N</i>	1.85	1.79	II
6 " "	12 <i>N</i>	2 <i>N</i> (1ml)	0.95	1.53	III

DISCUSSION

Results in Tables IA and II show that when the average concentration of HCl is below *N*/100, one mole of ascorbic acid requires two moles of nitrous acid. As the average strength of the acid increases, the proportion of nitrite falls and tends to one mole (Table I B). In nearly 10*N*-HCl, the ratio falls to 1:1.09. There is no contradiction between the results of Tables IA and II since HCl is being added from the burette so that effective concentration is low at all times.

On the other hand, when H_2SO_4 is used (Table IV), the ascorbic acid to nitrous acid ratio remains 1:2 at concentrations of H_2SO_4 up to 2*N*. Table III is again instructive. Here the mixture initially contains 0.1*mM* of nitrite and 0.128 *mM* of ascorbic acid; enough mineral acid is present to liberate the nitrous acid required. The reaction takes place after which the excess of the ascorbic acid is titrated back with iodine. It is found that in spite of an excess of ascorbic acid in weak HCl solutions (*N*/100), the ratio of the number of moles of ascorbic acid to NaNO₂ reacting remains 1:2. The ratio falls in strong HCl medium. This definitely establishes reactions of ascorbic acid with HNO₂, consuming a maximum of two moles in weak acid medium and a minimum of one mole in strong HCl per mole of ascorbic acid.

These results may be explained if we assume the following two reductions of nitrous acid in weak HCl (or H_2SO_4) and strong HCl respectively.

The production of NO should fall as the concentration of HCl is increased, so that a more feeble dark brown colour should develop on addition of fresh ferrous sulphate. Ultimately in 10*N*-HCl, only a trace of brown should persist. These expectations are confirmed strikingly by experiments. In small concentrations of H_2SO_4 and HCl (less than *N*/20)

therefore, only reaction (i) proceeds. As the HCl concentrations increase, reaction (ii) also appears and both reactions (i) and (ii) may operate simultaneously. In a high HCl concentration, reaction (ii) almost suppresses reaction (i). Increase in the concentration of H_2SO_4 seems to favour (ii) only slightly.

The question now arises whether reactions (i) and (ii) are simultaneous or consecutive. The balance of evidence appears to be in favour of a simultaneous reduction to NO and N_2O , but neither reaction appears to be catalysed by protons. In sulphuric acid mixtures, there is no appreciable increase in the rate of reaction (judged from the time taken in establishment of equilibrium) as the acid concentration is increased. In HCl mixtures, there is a considerable fall in the rate. It seems therefore that some specific effect of HCl is brought into play.

The idea that reactions (i) and (ii) are simultaneous is supported by the fact that NO is not easily reduced⁶. If the two reactions were consecutive, the ratio should have been 1:1 in all mixtures, where there is evidence for reaction (ii), since the reducing agent, namely, ascorbic acid, is in large excess during most parts of any titration.

It seems to us that the specific effect, to which we have referred, comes from the formation of NOCl in the mixture when enough HCl is present. It is this particle, which initiates reaction (ii) without affecting reaction (i) so that in different mixtures we observe varying ratios like 1.4, 1.2 or 1.09 (Table IB) instead of 1.0, if the reactions were consecutive, (ii) following (i). These ideas are further confirmed by the results in Tables III and V.

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